

Scaling of multicopy constructive interference of Gaussian states

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Quantum technology advances crucially depend on the scaling up of essential quantum resources. Their ideal multiplexing offers more significant gains in applications; however, the scaling of the nonidentical, fragile and varying resources is neither theoretically nor experimentally known. For bosonic systems, multimode interference is an essential tool already widely exploited to develop quantum technology. Here, we analyze, predict and compare essential scaling laws for a constructive interference of multiplexed nonclassical Gaussian states carrying information by displacement with weakly fluctuating squeezing in different multimode interference architectures. The signal-to-noise ratio quantifies the increase in displacement relative to the noise. We introduce the *gain-to-instability ratio* to numerically estimate the effect of unexplored resource instabilities in a large scale interference scheme. The use of the gain-to-instability ratio to quantify the scaling laws opens steps for extensive theoretical investigation of other bosonic resources and follow-up feasible experimental verification necessary for further development of these platforms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum physics and technology with bosonic systems intimately depend on the broad class of resource states, from primary Gaussian coherent and squeezed states [1, 2] to advanced non-Gaussian states [3–8], nonlinear phase states [9, 10] up to complex grid quantum states [9, 11] and multimode graph states [12, 13]. Nonclassical optical and atomic states play essential roles as the probes, codes, and critical ancillary states in all applications of bosonic systems, starting from quantum clocks [14–17] and metrology [18–23], communication [24–28], quantum computational algorithms [29–31] and continuing up to the development of resource states [32–35] and gates [36–38] towards scalable, fast and universal quantum computers [39]. Simultaneously, quantum non-Gaussian states of trapped ions and superconducting circuits demonstrated their first usefulness in the sensing [40–45] and quantum error correction [46–51].

In all such experiments, physical resources are not only naturally finite and imperfect. Moreover, their amount is never entirely identical across their copies and is typically not sufficiently stable, but varies across the copies. For the protocols, such resource states are theoretically modelled as realistic by considering finite energy and with the most dominant imperfection. However, these models broadly omit that they are different and not stable both in the amount of the resource and imperfections over multiple replicas of the resource. This seriously limits a critical analysis of feasibility, extendibility and scalability analysis for currently developed multicopy protocols. In many above mentioned applications, we then

use many different copies of such probes, codes, or ancillary states. Therefore, the overall performance depends on these differences in the resource states, their distributions, the protocols used, and the final figure of merit we aim for. These fundamental and practical thoughts open new questions about unexplored quantum scaling phenomena considering even slightly different resource states we use for applications. Such scalings will navigate further protocol developments and therefore, it can cross-fertilize developing quantum technology.

Essential and paramount nonclassical squeezed states can provide the first experimentally testable cases with different resources that are extensively scalable [29, 52–55]. Squeezed states as resources are already broadly applicable for quantum sensing [56–60] and quantum communication [24–28] but are also used for quantum computation primitives like Gaussian boson sampling [30] or for cluster state quantum computing [32, 52, 61, 62]. The time multiplexing of squeezed states has recently been scaled up to 10^6 modes [63]. It can allow experimental testing of the scaling laws with an unprecedented number of nonclassical states.

In this paper, we quantify how a figure of merit scales with the number of copies impacted by resource instability in the multicopy protocol, as illustrated in Fig.1(a). We consider the figure of merit, averaged over the instability of resources, as the protocol *gain*. We propose a dimensionless *gain-to-instability ratio* (GIR), which relates the gain to the standard deviation of the variation in the figure of merit, see Fig.1(b). We evaluate the increase in gain and GIR as a function of the number of copies. The GIR enables us to discuss scaling beyond the gain and to differentiate between unknown limitations of multicopy experiments, as demonstrated in Fig.1(c).

By employing the GIR, we analyse the constructive interference of the displaced Gaussian states with varying noise squeezing across the copies in different interference

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FIG. 1. Gain-to-instability quantification of quantum protocols: (a) multicopy protocols and their applications use quantum resources parametrised by $\mathbf{r} = (r_1, \dots, r_N)$ in a number N of finite, different and imperfect replicas of inputs quantified by the classical figure-of-merit $F_{in,i}(r_i)$, $i = 1, \dots, N$. The quantum states carrying resources are interacting in a quantum protocol that produces an output figure-of-merit $F_{out}^{(N)}(\mathbf{r})$ dependent on all the resources r_1, \dots, r_N . Each input is characterized by the same gain as average figure of merit $\langle F_{in}^{(1)} \rangle = \langle F_{in,i}(r_i) \rangle$ where $i = 1, \dots, N$. If the gains $\langle F_{out}^{(N)} \rangle > \langle F_{in}^{(1)} \rangle$ than any of the input, therefore it exhibits a multicopy gain. The gain may be considered nonclassical when it surpasses the classical benchmark $\langle F_{out,cl}^{(N)} \rangle$ and scalable if it is larger than $\langle F_{out}^{(N-1)} \rangle$, for any N . (b) To thoroughly evaluate the protocol, we propose an additional quantifier, the *gain-to-instability ratio* (GIR) for both inputs and outputs. We also extend the multicopy, nonclassical, and scalable criteria for GIR. As depicted in (c), the protocols with comparably scalable gains exhibit qualitatively different scaling of stability in the GIR. Protocol 1 (in blue) exhibits a highly stable scalability and, on the other hand, the protocol 2 (in orange) behaviour a lowly stable scalability.

architecture schemes and uncover their scalability. The figure of merit for our essential interference investigation is the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). SNR variation caused by unstable squeezing over many copies limits the scaling of GIR. Note that in the ideal case where all the input states are identical and perfectly stable states, the GIR diverges to infinity. Hence, limits on the GIR is a signature of imperfect input state copies. The scalings of the gain and GIR are suitable for immediate experimental tests [54, 71, 72] and facilitates further theoretical predictions for other Gaussian and quantum non-Gaussian resources used in bosonic systems and their applications.

II. FIGURE-OF-MERIT: SNR

Considering the Gaussian approximation of bosonic states, a signal conveying information in a single variable is encoded as a classical coherent displacement. Using interferometric schemes from linear optics, Gaussian

noise cannot be reduced, even with linear measurements, feedforward control or postselection. However, the displacements can be accumulated from multiple inputs into a single output by a constructive interference. This corresponds to a scenario presented in Fig.1a.

Gaussian protocols are primarily designed to achieve maximal mean displacement, after which quantum noise is assessed. Therefore, it is essential to compare the mean displacement from a constructive interference with the standard deviation of quantum noise, rather than examining them separately. To achieve this, we utilise a widely accepted figure of merit – the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), which is calculated by dividing the mean displacement by the standard deviation of the noise associated with the displaced output state. Increasing SNR is needed to distinguish displacements with greater certainty. It is an essential operational prerequisite for any multi-copy interference of signals before any application is considered. The SNR for specific variables is also more detailed than the overall state fidelity [67, 68]. When the standard de-

FIG. 2. Different architectures of interferometric schemes: (a) Pyramidal architecture is an interferometer composed solely of balanced beam splitters. Each pair of input modes interacts, and the constructive output modes of two adjacent beam splitters are utilised as the input modes of the next beam splitter in the interferometer. At the output, this pyramid ensures full constructive interference of mean inputs in the X variable. The output is verified by detecting this variable. (b) Sequential architecture must employ transmittances $t_i = i/(i + 1)$ to achieve the same constructive interference in the output as the pyramidal strategy, with identical mean and standard deviation. (c) Dynamical and fixed loop architectures, where the input modes are temporally multiplexed in time-bins, interfere on a single beam splitter with transmittance t_i in such a way that the constructive interference output is re-injected into the first input and interacts with a new squeezed state. The transmittance t_i can vary dynamically as $t_i = i/(i + 1)$ to create a fully equivalent output to the pyramidal and sequential architectures. In simpler scenarios, the transmittance is optimised to a single fixed value t^* according to the number N of the interfering copies to achieve maximal output mean displacement, or alternatively is simply fixed to $t_i = 0.5$. These simpler strategies do achieve maximal mean displacement at the output, however, they can still partially increase the SNR.

viation of noise varies over the copies, the SNR fluctuates, and these variations are significant for the protocol gain and stability. This becomes more complex if the interference protocol simultaneously utilises multiple copies with varying noise, as in many recent experiments [27, 32, 37, 43, 52, 63].

Considering fluctuating SNR as the figure of merit in our analysis, the mean SNR reflects an improvement of the constructive interference in the protocol, generally visualized in Fig.1(a). The output mean SNR for N inputs must surpass that of a single input to ascertain whether the multicopy inputs are genuinely advantageous. Moreover, the output SNR of nonclassical protocols must exceed that of their classical counterparts. Additionally, scalability requires that the output SNR increases with N . To account for fluctuations in SNR caused by instability, the standard deviation of SNR must be lower than its mean with the increasing N . Therefore, the gain-to-instability ratio (GIR) can be proposed for SNR following this approach, as introduced in Fig.1(b). Subsequently, multicopy, nonclassical, and scalable criteria must also extend to GIR. Analysing the impact of instability in SNR on the protocol using GIR is essential, the mean SNR cannot specify such instability, as illustrated in Fig. 1(c).

Before considering any applications involving numerous copies of the Gaussian states, it is essential to evaluate the fundamental scalability of constructive interference under varying squeezed standard deviation over copies. The goal is to enhance the SNR, thereby extending previous protocols that involved only two copies [69, 70]. Different architectures of linear interference protocols, as illustrated in Fig. 2, are currently distinctive due to their high feasibility with numerous copies of Gaussian states in laboratories. Therefore, it is possible to demonstrate a scaling of the average SNR under

variations in squeezing noise from copy to copy. However, SNR now becomes a random variable whose average does not provide complete information. SNR fluctuations can be diverse, and their behaviour remains entirely unknown and unexplored, both theoretically and experimentally, even in such basic interference protocols. The risk is that these, even minor, fluctuations can expand faster with N than the average SNR. Such protocol functionality can be significantly degraded by slightly varying squeezed standard deviation compared to the ideal case. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis must be performed both theoretically and experimentally, which will uncover quantum interference protocols in a new, much more realistic designs. Only after a thorough understanding and verification of the scalability of interference effects in terms of SNR can the analysis of applications with different figures of merit proceed with comparisons to this essential SNR scalability.

III. INTERFEROMETRIC ARCHITECTURES

To concentrate mean displacements from all inputs into a single output, three configurations illustrated in Fig.2 are possible in linear interferometry: pyramidal, sequential, and dynamic loop. The pyramidal and sequential architectural configurations consist of $N - 1$ beam splitters, whereas the loop architecture employs a dynamically variable beam splitter. If the interferometry is ideal, they are equivalent. However, in realistic, slightly imperfect interferometers, they may differ. In our theoretical analysis, we will consider the case of ideal and stable interferometry, but with realistic and unstable noise in the input states.

In the pyramid shown in Fig. 2(a), one must combine every pair of input modes on a *balanced* beam splitter. After this initial layer of interaction, one should collect all the $N/2$ constructive interference output modes from

the beam splitter of the first layer and use them as the input modes for the second layer of the balanced beam splitter. This process should be repeated until only one final constructive output mode remains and all the other output modes are traced out.

The sequential architecture in Fig. 2(b) involves the interference of the first two inputs on a balanced beam splitter. Next, the constructive interference output is combined with a new third replica of the inputs at an unbalanced beam splitter with a transmittance of $2/3$. This process should be repeated by interfering the output of with the $(i + 1)$ th input on an unbalanced beam splitter with transmittance $t_i = i/(i + 1)$. Finally, after interfering all the N inputs on this interferometer, one ideally achieves an output with the same output as the pyramidal architecture (see Fig. 2(b)).

The dynamic loop architecture illustrated in Fig.2(c) employs an interference of temporally multiplexed inputs in time-bins at a single beam splitter, while also utilising a varying transmittance $t_i = i/(i + 1)$. This design is exceptionally compact but necessitates an additional delay element to ideally achieve the same output as the pyramidal and sequential architectures.

Conversely, simpler architectures can be considered to achieve an output with sufficient SNR and reduced control of the interferometer. They may replace previous architectures, which could be more challenging to implement. For instance, one might envision a loop architecture with time-multiplexed inputs (see again Fig.2(c)), where the constructive interference output interferes with the subsequent input, but now on a beam splitter with a fixed yet optimised transmittance t^* or by setting the fixed transmittance without optimisation.

IV. RESULTS: PYRAMIDAL, SEQUENTIAL AND DYNAMICAL LOOP STRATEGY

Let us first consider the multicopy interference of classical states of bosonic modes. By interfering two replicas of an ideal coherent state (with position and momentum standard deviations $\Delta x = \Delta p = 1$ and position mean value $\bar{x}^{(1)} = x_0$) on a balanced beam-splitter interferometer, the state in the constructive interference output mode is a coherent state with displacement $\bar{x}^{(2)} = \sqrt{2}x_0$. For the coherent states with imposed additive classical thermal noise with $\Delta x_0 = \Delta p_0 = \sqrt{1 + \sigma_0^2}$, the displacement increases by the same factor $\sqrt{2}$, but the standard deviation remains $\sqrt{1 + \sigma_0^2}$.

One can extend this architecture to an interferometer that is feeded with N coherent input states. If all N input states are pure coherent states with identical initial displacement $x_i = x_0$ (where the subscript i labels the input mode number), the coherent states in the constructive interference output mode will have a displacement $\bar{x}_{out,cl}^{(N)} = \sqrt{N}x_0$. In the case of perfectly interfering N input coherent states on a linear interferometer consti-

tuted of balanced beam-splitters is

$$\text{SNR}_{out,cl}^{(N)} = \frac{\bar{x}_{out,cl}^{(N)}}{\Delta x_{out,cl}^{(N)}} = \sqrt{N}x_0. \quad (1)$$

This ideal interference of coherent states constitutes our classical benchmark in the scalability of the signal in a passive interferometer. Expectedly, if thermal noise is imposed, the standard deviation remains invariant and only reduces Eq.(1) by a multiplicative factor $\sqrt{1 + \sigma_0^2}$. Moreover, considering noise figure $\text{NF} = \text{SNR}_{out}^{(N)} / \text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)}$ between the output SNR and the input SNR after the interference we gain $\text{NF}_{cl} = \sqrt{N}$ for all classical ideal interference.

However, when the inputs are not stable over the statistical ensemble and slowly drift or diffuse in the signal or noise, the interference may change substantially. To follow physics closely as needed in operational approach, we consider quantum optical platform, broadly known to the bosonic community and with large experimental feasibility of such multicopy protocols [10, 32, 54, 71, 72]. For nearly ideal classical light from shot-noise limit laser only the signal amplitude x_0 can vary at longer time scale following a Gaussian distribution due to thermal pump changes [73]. The stabilized standard deviation $\Delta x = 1$ is practically unaffected. Such a stable shot-noise limit is essential for calibrating the scale of position and momentum quadrature measurements [74].

By taking the instability in amplitude into account, we assume the input signal is in the form $x_i = x_0 + \delta x_i$, where δx_i is a random variable following a centered normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{x_0}^2)$ where $\sigma_{x_0}^2$ is the variance in the signal distribution. The SNR averaged on the displacement fluctuations reduces to the classical SNR in Eq.(1) as: $\langle \text{SNR}_{out,cl}^{(N)} \rangle_{\delta x_i} = \sqrt{N} (x_0 + \langle \delta x \rangle) = \sqrt{N}x_0$, where $\delta x = (\delta x_1, \dots, \delta x_i, \dots, \delta x_N)^T$ is the signal fluctuation vector. Hence, the fluctuations in signal are statistically irrelevant for mean SNR in the regime of large N . If the laser is not shot-noise-limited but Δx_0 is stabilized, it follows the same pattern and finally, such classical multimode interference instability in the signal has always $\text{NF} = \sqrt{N}$.

Nonclassical squeezed states can be used to carry information encoded in the displacement with smaller noise. The replacement of coherent states by displaced squeezed states with a stable noise as input of our linear interferometer will not affect the mean displacement in the protocol which follows the one of the classical case. However, the standard deviation in the x -quadrature of the output mode will be reduced by a factor of e^{-r} , where r is squeezing parameter proportional to pump amplitude. Compared to the coherent state variance, the squeezing leads to

$$\text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} = \frac{\bar{x}_{out,sq}^{(N)}}{\Delta x_{out,sq}^{(N)}} = \sqrt{N}e^r x_0. \quad (2)$$

Hence, the effect of using stable squeezed states is to in-

crease the classical SNR from Eq.(1) by a multiplicative factor e^r while keeping the scaling of \sqrt{N} unaffected reflected by an ideal noise figure $\text{NF} = \sqrt{N}$, still same as for the classical case. As the squeezing of the input mode states is stable ($r_i = r$ for all i 's), then Eq.(2) is the upper bound on the SNR that can be reached.

However, when the shot-noise-limited laser light with an instability in amplitude discussed above is used as the pump in optical parametric oscillator (OPO) to generate squeezing [73], the squeezing level can vary. For squeezed states with $\Delta x = e^{-r}$, where r is the squeezing parameter linearly depending on the uncertain amplitude of the pump [73], SNR and NF begin to change substantially due to their averages of the exponent of varying r . These results are in our example obtained by modelling the effect of laser amplitude instability on the squeezing properties of the output squeezed states in a $\chi^{(2)}$ squeezing process typically used in optical parametric amplifiers. Note that the results might be different if the squeezing process is made by a $\chi^{(3)}$ process like four-wave-mixing [75–77], as the squeezing is proportional to the amplitudes of two pumps. To demonstrate our methodology, we model that the only source of instability is the squeezing parameter. Phase instability affects both classical coherent and non-classical states, such as squeezed-displaced states, and is significant for certain experiments. Nonetheless, these instabilities can be mitigated through phase-locking with a classical light beam. However, such techniques do not address the instability of the output coherent amplitude and squeezing from a parametric oscillator or amplifier, which typically differ from pump fluctuations. Therefore, we initially concentrate on these aspects to demonstrate the approach in this manuscript. Future experimental verification might incorporate phase fluctuations; however, including them would complicate the presentation of the method. In our model of interference of squeezed states, the effect of a pure-loss on the input modes is to reduce the SNR but it increase the GIR as it stabilizes the squeezing fluctuations (see Fig. 7(b)). We refer the interested reader to appendix VIII C for details on the effect of losses on the SNR and GIR.

Therefore, in a more realistic description of squeezing from the OPO, one need to take into account the amplitude instability of the pump laser for the squeezing generation that translates in *independent* changes δr_i of the squeezing parameter r_i of each input mode around a stable value r_0 . Hence, the N replicas of input pure squeezed states are considered to have identical signal values $x_i = x_0$ but independently varying squeezing parameter value $r_i = r_0 + \delta r_i$ where, similarly to the signal fluctuations, the δr_i 's are assumed to be distributed from a Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_r^2)$. This assumption is relevant in experimental situations where σ_r is independent of N , therefore, we have no prior limits to scale it up until the replicas interfere. The input signal-to-noise ratio, as our figure of merit, is defined as $\text{SNR}_{in,i} = x_0 \exp r_i$ where r_i is the squeezing parameter varying for each copy. Already

the single-copy average $\langle \text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)} \rangle = x_0 \exp(r_0) \exp(\sigma_r^2/2)$ exponentially increases with the variance σ_r^2 of that Gaussian fluctuations. However, the standard deviation $\Delta \text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)} = x_0 \exp(r_0) \exp(\sigma_r^2/2) \sqrt{\exp(\sigma_r^2) - 1}$ and therefore the uncertainty in SNR grows faster than its mean value and there is no real positive gain. It suggests that comparison of mean SNR and its standard deviation is important to understand the results. To make comparison quantitative, a stability ratio $\langle \text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)} \rangle / \Delta \text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)} = 1/\sqrt{\exp(\sigma_r^2) - 1}$ describes purely the effect of the varying squeezing standard deviation irrespectively to x_0 and r_0 . Note for later, for the small σ_r , we take the series expansion to the first order in $\sigma_r^2/2$, and obtain $\langle \text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)} \rangle \approx x_0(\exp r_0)(1 + \sigma_r^2/2)$ and $\langle \text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)} \rangle / \Delta \text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)} \approx 1/\sigma_r - \sigma_r/4$.

In this scenario with varying squeezing over the copies, the SNR at the constructive output of the ideal beam-splitter network is

$$\text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} = \frac{\sqrt{N} x_0}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N e^{-2r_i}}} = \frac{N e^{r_0} x_0}{\sqrt{\sum_i^N e^{-2\delta r_i}}}, \quad (3)$$

by assuming the accumulated mean displacement in the nominator without any change as it is stable or with only additive Gaussian noise as described above. Generally, the uncertainty in Eq.(3) over δr_i can be analysed only numerically. However, by assuming that the fluctuations in the squeezing parameters δr_i are small (meaning that $\sigma_r^2 \ll 1$), we can approximate Eq.(3) in series up to the second order in δr_i 's and take the average. Note that the δr_i 's are considered to be independent and identically distributed from the normal centered distribution. Hence, they are assumed to have zero-mean $\langle \delta r \rangle = 0$ and to be uncorrelated. The approximated mean SNR from Eq.(3) is

$$\langle \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} \rangle \approx \sqrt{N} e^{r_0} x_0 \left(1 + \left(\frac{3}{2N} - 1 \right) \sigma_r^2 \right), \quad (4)$$

which in the asymptotic limit of large N is converging to:

$$\langle \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} \rangle \rightarrow \sqrt{N} e^{r_0} x_0 (1 - \sigma_r^2) \quad (5)$$

that can be compared with input $\langle \text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)} \rangle \approx x_0(\exp r_0)(1 + \sigma_r^2/2)$. Remarkably, by the constructive interference, the small random differences in squeezing of the input modes only slightly and linearly modifies the ideal mean output SNR by a multiplicative prefactor $(1 - \sigma_r^2)$. This is also visible in only small decrease of $\text{NF} = \sqrt{N} (1 - \sigma_r^2)$. Hence the scaling factor \sqrt{N} for the mean SNR is preserved for σ_r significantly smaller than 1.

However, similarly as for the input SNR, we must compare the average $\langle \text{SNR}_{out}^{(N)} \rangle$ from Eq.(3) with the uncertainty in such SNR by a standard deviation $\Delta \text{SNR}_{out}^{(N)} = \sqrt{\langle (\text{SNR}_{out}^{(N)})^2 \rangle - \langle \text{SNR}_{out}^{(N)} \rangle^2}$ to understand our results

and their scaling. Then, their ratio will determine the role of the squeezing instability. The larger is such ratio, smaller is the effect of the squeezing instability on the SNR determined by Eq.(3). We utilise the standard deviation in the denominator of GIR to obtain a conservative characteristic of the varying resources.

Motivated by this, we propose a general outline of this approach. Having a figure-of-merit F for the protocol, we consider the *average gain* $\langle F_{out}^{(N)} \rangle$ using N copies of resources that are not stable. We define a *gain-to-instability ratio* (GIR) by normalizing the gain by a standard deviation $\langle \Delta F_{out}^{(N)} \rangle$. The closest notion to the GIR in classical signal processing is, to our knowledge, the Amount of Fading (AoF) of the instantaneous SNR encountered for example in the field of wireless communication [78]. In the fields of quantum information and communication, fading has been described in [79–82] where unstable transmittivity has been used, but GIR was not defined, considered nor used. In the unrealistic case of ideally stable identical copies, the GIR diverges, similarly to the SNR in the unrealistic case of no fluctuations. Analogically, as for the signal-to-noise ratio in classical signal analysis, $\text{GIR} > 1$ is at least needed, and a faster increase with N makes scaling of averaged gain more reliable. A saturation of GIR limits the scalability of reliable protocols under the varying resources, although the average gain scales further with N . Therefore, although different protocols and their architectures might have a nearly comparable scaling of the gain in $\langle F_{out}^{(N)} \rangle$ over N copies, they may differ substantially in the gain reliability quantified by the GIR. Also the opposite situation can happen, the architectures might have different gain in $\langle F_{out}^{(N)} \rangle$ over N copies, but GIR might suggest similar gain reliability.

Let us continue our guiding example with the varying squeezing and figure-of-merit being SNR. Although such GIR is essential, its full evaluation is also possible only numerically, even in our simple case, making the outcome not simply predictable and nontrivial. For the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures, the GIR can be approximately evaluated in the second-order expansion to predict

$$\text{GIR}_{\text{SNR}} = \frac{\langle \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} \rangle}{\Delta \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)}} \approx \sqrt{N} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_r} + \left(\frac{3}{2N} - 1 \right) \sigma_r \right), \quad (6)$$

which complements the approximative formula for mean SNR given by Eq. (4). Differently, the standard deviation σ_r , not the variance σ_r^2 , determines Eq. (6). In the limit of very large number N of input modes, (6) converges to

$$\text{GIR}_{\text{SNR}} = \frac{\langle \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} \rangle}{\Delta \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)}} \rightarrow \sqrt{N} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_r} - \sigma_r \right). \quad (7)$$

First, let us appreciate that the scaling in Eq.(7) depends of the number of input states N exactly like Eq.(5) for the

mean SNR. On the other hand, GIR in Eq.(7) does not depend on the input mean displacement x_0 and squeezing r_0 similarly as the noise figure $\text{NF} = \sqrt{N}(1 - \sigma_r^2)$. Second, crucially, gain-to-instability ratio Eq.(7) decreases inversely to σ_r , that makes reduction much faster than the average SNR Eq.(4). Therefore, increasing the number N of input copies allows to compensate such decreases much slowly than for the mean in Eq.(5) and corresponding $\text{NF} = \sqrt{N}(1 - \sigma_r^2)$ and irrespectively to x_0 and r_0 . Considering $\sigma_r = 0.1$ and $\sigma_r = 0.2$ and limit of large N , NF per a single copy reduces negligibly only from 0.99 to 0.96, however, GIR drops more from 9.9 to 4.8. The later case with $\sigma_r = 0.2$ requires four times more copies to reach the same GIR as the former one with $\sigma_r = 0.1$. GIR is much more demanding to compensate by more copies for these architectures than NF. Therefore, GIR must be evaluated to complement analysis of the gains in the multicopy squeezing protocols.

V. DISCUSSION: FIXED LOOP STRATEGIES, NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND MEASUREMENT-INDUCED SQUEEZING

The pyramidal, loop and dynamical loop architectures lead to an SNR scaling law proportional to \sqrt{N} with a $\text{GIR} = \langle \text{SNR} \rangle / \Delta \text{SNR}$ that also scale as \sqrt{N} , as visible in Fig.3. However, the experimental setup to realize pyramidal and sequential architecture use of $N - 1$ beam splitters and the dynamical loop architecture needs to dynamically vary the single beam splitter. Therefore, it is worth to investigate a more experiment-friendly loop architecture consisting of only single beam-splitter with some fixed transmittance t that can be optimized respective to the number N of copies to reach maximal mean displacement at the output. For the N input copies, we approach

$$\text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} = \frac{x_0 \sum_{i=1}^N \tau_i^{\frac{1}{2}}}{e^{-r_0} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \tau_i e^{-2\delta r_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\tau_i = \begin{cases} t^{N-1} & \text{if } i = 1, \\ (1-t)t^{N-i} & \text{if } i > 1 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

are accumulated transmittances at the output. Note that in the ideal case without fluctuations, Eq.(8) denominator is identically equal to one and, therefore, only mean displacement in numerator is optimized.

The values of the transmittance $t = t^*$ become very close to one for large N and can be numerically obtained from the maximum of approximative mean displacement $x_0 \sqrt{1 - t^*} (\sqrt{t^*} - t^{*N/2}) / (\sqrt{t^*} - t^*)$ determining nominator of (8). Approximative $t^* \approx 1 - 2.4/N$ is able to reach the mean displacement $0.9x_0\sqrt{N}$, i.e. 90% of the displacement $x_0\sqrt{N}$ of the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures. For small $\sigma_r^2 \ll 1$, the approximated

FIG. 3. Constructive interference of N equally displaced squeezed states with varying standard deviation of noise for the different architectures. The parameter values are the same for all architectures and are set to $x_0 = 0.5$, $r_0 = 2$, $\sigma_r = 0.5$. (a) The mean signal-to-noise ratio $\langle \text{SNR} \rangle$: continuous lines represent the ideally stable squeezing for each architecture. The dotted lines account for the squeezing instability. The blue line corresponds to the pyramidal, sequential, and dynamical loop architectures as defined by Eq.(2). For the fixed loop architecture outlined in Eq.(8), the orange line denotes a transmittance t^* , the green line represents a fixed transmittance $t_i = (N-1)/N$, while the purple line indicates the fixed $t_i = 0.5$, independent of N . The blue dotted line relates to Eq.(3), and for comparison, the blue dashed line is provided by the approximate Eq.(4) (except for very small N , which is not shown on the graph). The dotted orange, green, and purple lines adhere to Eq.(8) for $t = t^*$, $t_i = 1 - 1/N$, and $t_i = 0.5$, respectively. For comparison, the yellow points indicate the average SNR for measurement-induced displacements from varying two-mode squeezed states [83, 84]. The black curve represents the classical limit as given by Eq. (1), where the input states are coherent states. (b) The gain-to-instability ratio $\text{GIR}_{\text{SNR}} = \langle \text{SNR} \rangle / \Delta \text{SNR}$: The blue points correspond to the GIR from numerical simulations, and the blue dashed line represents their exponential fit by $1.5 \times N^{0.51}$. For comparison, the blue continuous line is the approximate Eq.(6); its asymptotic behaviour, as described in Eq.(7), is indistinguishable from the blue continuous line. The yellow points correspond to the GIR for measurement-induced displacements from varying two-mode squeezed states. The orange points represent the GIR numerically simulated for the loop architecture with optimised transmittances $t = t^*(N)$. The dashed orange line is their exponential fit $3.5 \times N^{0.27}$. Finally, the green points curve represents the data for the loop architecture with transmittance fixed at $(N-1)/N$, which saturates quickly. It is similar to the purple curve for the loop architecture with $t = 0.5$, which performs poorly. Note that all the parameters and exponential fitting values are in Tables I and II; see Appendix VIII D.

$\langle \text{SNR}_{\text{out},sq}^{(N)} \rangle$ approaches $0.9\sqrt{N}e^{r_0}x_0(1-\sigma_r^2)$ lowered by the smaller mean displacement. Although only a single beam splitter is sufficient, a precise setting of the transmittance close to unity is still needed for large number of input modes N .

To simplify strategies further, one can fix transmittance of the beam splitter without such optimization. We have taken two possible values to be a fixed balanced transmittance $t_1 = 1 - 1/N$, and $t_2 = 1/2$ for a comparison, both corresponding to the last and first beamsplitter for the sequential and dynamical loop strategies. In the former case of $t_1 = 1 - 1/N$, we can approximately reach mean displacement $0.79x_0\sqrt{N}$ still 80% close to pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop method and also $\langle \text{SNR}_{\text{out},sq}^{(N)} \rangle$ changes satisfactorily by the same factor. In the later case, it is quickly saturated over N to maximally $x_0(\sqrt{2} + 1)$, being negligible to all previous cases and inefficient.

In order to test these analytical results and, mainly, to predict GIR for different simpler strategies, we simulate the resulting first and second moment at the constructing interference output of our linear interferometer and study their scaling up properties. These numerical results are performed by sampling the squeezing parameter r from a normal distribution with some fixed standard deviation

σ_r and mean value r_0 . Hence, the squeezing parameter for each input pure squeezed state is $r_i = r_0 + \delta r_i$ where the i labels the input mode number and $\delta r_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_r)$. By using Eq. (3) and Eq.(8), one can simulate the varying output SNR in order to estimate the average $\langle \text{SNR} \rangle$, for the different architectures.

The simulation is carried out for each number N of input state from $N = 2$ to $N = 1000$ and repeated 100 times to access the $\langle \text{SNR} \rangle$ for each N . In Fig.3(a), each diamond point is generated numerically as described. One can see that the result displayed in Fig.3(a) show that the behaviour of the SNR for the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures (in blue) and fixed loop architecture with optimized transmittivity t^* (in orange) and $t_1 = 1 - 1/N$ (in green) are very similar. Indeed, the scaling law of \sqrt{N} is conserved for all architecture and only the pre-factors are affected by the choice of architecture. However, the difference between the ideal case without any squeezing instability (solid blue line) and the numerical evaluations of Eq.(3) including moderate squeezing fluctuations $\sigma_r = 0.5$ (dotted blue line) is already noticeable, the scaling with \sqrt{N} remains and only prefactors change when $t = t^*$ and $t = t_1$. On the other hand, for the loop with fixed balanced transmittance $t_2 = 0.5$ (in purple), the SNR is low, saturated due

to previously analysed mean displacement and, therefore, breaks the classical limit at same N (solid black line). The numerator simply has converging series over N for any constant t explaining the unscalability of such fixed transmittivity architecture and need for t depended on N .

We also point out that the numerical data (dotted blue in Fig.3(a)) from Eq.(3) and the approximated SNR (dashed blue line in Fig.3(a)) from Eq. (4) are in good agreement. However, such agreement can strongly depend on larger values of the σ_r describing squeezing instability. Still, the gain in SNR from even unstable squeezed fluctuations in the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architecture is not critically reduced and remains significantly higher than the classical limit (solid black line). Indeed, even under its instability, the squeezing substantially contribute to the enhancement of the SNR compared to the classical case.

In Fig.3(b), we display the numerical results for the gain-to-instability ratio (GIR) to study the realistic impact of varying squeezing on stability of the gain in SNR. We keep the transmittance optimized to reach maximal mean displacement at the output as for the Fig.3(a). A substantial difference can now be seen between the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures in a contrast to fixed loop architectures. Indeed, while the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures architecture has the GIR (blue points) that approximately scales as $N^{1/2}$, the loop architecture with fixed optimized $t = t^*$ scales very differently as $N^{1/4}$ (orange points) and, therefore, saturates much faster. The loop architectures with a fixed transmittance $t = t_1 = 1 - 1/N$ (green points) have essentially saturating behaviour similar to strategy with fixed $t = t_2 = 1/2$ that was already inefficient in Fig.3(a). The transmission optimization of the loop architecture with a single transmittance t can moderately compromised beyond the mean displacement discussed here, between the mean SNR and the GIR. For an example, in Fig.3(b) the loop strategy can reach $\text{GIR}_{\text{SNR}}^{(1000)} \approx 30$ at the cost of slight decrease of the mean SNR to $\langle \text{SNR}_{\text{out},sq}^{(1000)} \rangle \approx 75$ and mean displacement to $13.4x_0$ for $N = 1000$.

It is an experimentally testable example showing that such saturation of the GIR qualitatively limits the scaling-up reliability of the architecture under resource instability despite the SNR can behave rather similarly with the same power in the scaling. Hence, the difference between the different architectures must be accessed in terms of the new gain-to-instability ratio. The mean gain in the figure-of-merit is not sufficient to describe influence of resources that are not stable and can overestimate fixed loop architectures.

This analysis of the impact of varying single-mode squeezing can be compared with the measurement-induced alternative that employs a combination of two varying orthogonal squeezed states. Each two-mode squeezing copy i can be generated by mixing

two orthogonally squeezed vacuum states with minimal variances $\sigma_{A,i}^2 = \exp(-2r_0)\exp(-2\delta_{A,i})$ and $\sigma_{B,i}^2 = \exp(-2r_0)\exp(-2\delta_{B,i})$ in pairs modes A,i and B,i at the balanced beamsplitter coupling. Measuring a value x_m of one of the squeezed variables in the output mode of each copy, the conditional state has a displacement $x_{0,i} = x_m(\sigma_{A,i}^2 - \sigma_{B,i}^{-2})/(\sigma_{A,i}^2 + \sigma_{B,i}^{-2})$ and variance $\sigma_i^2 = 2\sigma_{A,i}^2\sigma_{B,i}^{-2}/(\sigma_{A,i}^2 + \sigma_{B,i}^{-2})$ that appear in the other output mode of each copy. In the ideal limit of stable ($\delta_{A,i} = \delta_{B,i} = 0$) and large ($r_0 \gg 1$) squeezing $x_{0,i} \approx x_m$ and $\sigma_i^2 \approx 2\exp(-2r_0)$. As the variance σ_i^2 of each copy is twice as large as in the previous single-mode cases, the measurement-induced preparation is less efficient. It already reduces ideally stable single-copy $\text{SNR}_{in}^{(1)}$ by factor $1/\sqrt{2} \approx 0.7$. Following the pyramidal, sequential, and dynamic loop architecture for varying squeezing, the reduction propagates and $\text{SNR}_{out}^{(N)}$ decreases by the same factor in this ideal limit. For stable squeezing parameter r_0 , we reach ideally $\text{SNR}_{out}^{(N)} \approx \sqrt{N}x_0 \sinh(2r_0)/\sqrt{\cosh(2r_0)}$.

Outside this idealistic limit, the varying squeezing parameters $\delta_{A,i}$ and $\delta_{B,i}$ affect also the mean displacements, however, $\langle \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} \rangle$ does not significantly change for moderate squeezing instability $\sigma_r/r_0 < 1$. Therefore, $\langle \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} \rangle$ reduces further as visible from numerical simulation in Fig.3(a) (yellow points) by the rise in the standard deviation of the SNR's denominator. If the displacement is used for feedforward control of the output after the measurement of x_m with a feedforward gain adjusted to minimise the variance of the output for the stable and necessarily known r_0 , the nearly same $\langle \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} \rangle$ is deterministically obtained for the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures in the limit of moderate instability $\sigma_r/r_0 < 1$. Note that beyond this limit, known r_0 helps to deterministic feedforward strategy to achieve higher $\langle \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} \rangle$. Despite the reduction of $\langle \text{SNR}_{out,sq}^{(N)} \rangle$ for both the measurement-induced strategies involving two-mode states, the GIR remains comparable for the pyramidal, sequential, and dynamical loop architectures to the single-mode strategies described by Eq.(6) for a moderate instability $\sigma_r/r_0 < 1$, as shown in Fig.3(b) (yellow points). As measurement-induced squeezing is extensively utilised as a resource for continuous-variable protocols, it demonstrates that moderate squeezing instability has a comparable impact to the direct squeezing discussed above.

Based on Eqs.(2,4,5), we can discuss in detail the effect of σ_r on the mean SNR in Fig. 4(a). The first observation is that the approximated expression for the mean SNR given by Eq.(4), depicted as a dotted blue line, tends to the asymptotic expression of the SNR in Eq.(5) already for a number of inputs of order $N \approx 10$. A second observation is that as N increases, the approximation of the SNR deviates from the ideal mean SNR more rapidly as σ_r increases. A third point is that when considering the approximated mean SNR in Fig. 4(a), one can

FIG. 4. Constructive interference in the different architectures at Fig.2 as functions of (a,c) squeezing instability σ_r and (b,d) average squeezing r_0 . Parameters are $x_0 = 0.5$, $r_0 = 2$, $\sigma_r = 0.5$ as in Fig.3, unless free parameter. Note that the colors and thickness codes used are the same in all the panels of Fig.4. In Fig.4(a), the horizontal continuous blue line is for ideal behaviour in the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures, orange lines corresponds to the loop architecture the optimized transmittance t^* and green lines are for fixed transmittance equal $(N - 1)/N$. Trios of lines are for $N = 3$ (thinner lines), $N = 30$ and $N = 300$ (boldest lines) input copies (from bottom to top lines). The points of corresponding colours are the results of numerical simulations for different strategies. The blue decreasing lines are for approximated (Eq. (4); dotted line) and asymptotic (Eq. (5); dotted line) formulas. Note that when N increase the approximated and asymptotic formula's for SNR become arbitrarily close and appears like a continuous line. This means that the asymptotic behaviour of the SNR is reached already for a number of modes N of order 10. In Fig.4(b), the colors and thickness codes are used for different architectures (colors) and number of input copies (thickness) for $N = 3$ (bottom thin lines), $N = 30$ (middle medium lines) and $N = 300$ (top bold lines). The dots shows the numerical simulations. For the blue colors, approximated (dotted) and asymptotic (dotted) formula's are displayed. Note that when N increase the approximated and asymptotic formula's for SNR become arbitrarily close and appears like a continuous line for $N = 300$. For Fig.4(c), the GIR is showed for different architectures (colors) and different number of input modes (thickness) as a function of the standard deviation σ_r . Here, only the numerical data is displayed. The dots are joined by a continuous line in order to emphasize the decreasing of the GIR with the standard deviation σ_r . Finally, in Fig.4(d), the GIR is showed for different architectures (colors) and different number of input modes (thickness) as a function of the mean squeezing r_0 . Here again, only the numerical is displayed and the dots are joined by straight lines in order to emphasize their behaviour. Here, one can see that, for all architecture (colors) and number of input modes N (thickness), the GIR is not very sensitive to the mean squeezing r_0 .

observe that the SNR drops quickly when σ_r increases. On the other hand, the numerically simulated mean SNR by averaging the formula (3) represented by the dots is higher and decays much slowly for larger σ_r for all architectures, especially for larger N . A minor observation in Fig. 4(a) is that the fixed loop architecture provides a higher mean SNR for small N in the ideal case than the pyramidal architecture. However, pyramidal architecture offers a higher SNR for larger N .

By taking the mean squeezing r_0 as a variable for the SNR in the different architecture, we see in Fig.4(b), that

they all scale exponentially up with r_0 for all N . Similarly as in Fig. 4(a) the fixed loop architecture has a higher SNR for small number of modes N while the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures provide a higher SNR for larger number of input modes N . Moreover, the larger the number of input states in Fig. 4(a), the larger becomes the difference in SNR between the different architectures. This shows that a larger number of varying squeezings in input states makes the discrimination between different architectures more visible. However, the relative difference between the architecture

seems to be constant. Hence, the different scaling for each architecture is impacted by the fluctuation σ_r rather than the mean squeezing r_0 .

The Fig.4(c) shows that the GIR decreases with the fluctuations in squeezing σ_r according to its approximations in Eqs.(6,7). On one hand, in the limit of small fluctuations $\sigma_r \ll 1$, the GIR is diverging to infinity. On the other hand, in the limit of largely varying squeezings, the GIR of the different architectures and different number of input modes converges to values smaller than 10. In this regime of large fluctuations, the number of modes do not play as significant role in discriminating the performances of the different protocols. Hence, one can conclude that the interest of using GIR resides in the regime of moderate to low variations of the squeezings in input states where its discriminating power between between the different architecture at different scales is the largest. As a final remark for Fig.4(c), the GIR typically increase with the number of modes (see for example the lines in orange and blue). However, in the case of the architecture using a beam-spitter with a fixed transmittance of $(N - 1)/N$ (green lines), the GIR do not vary much with the number of modes N . This is the signature of a saturation in the GIR as it can be observed in Fig.4(b).

Finally, Fig.4(d) allows us to conclude that the GIR is independent of the mean squeezing of the input states r_0 . Hence, the GIR is only determined by the number of input states and the varying squeezing of these states as expected. Therefore, the GIR can be used independently to the squeezing regime.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We provide a methodology to analyse instability of resources used in multicopy bosonic protocols and applications by introducing gain-to-instability ratio.

Already for Gaussian states we demonstrated an essential difference in the scaling properties of the architectures. The average gains represented by a signal-to-noise ratio for the displacement might be very similar, but for the pyramidal, sequential and loop architecture architecture, the gain-to-instability ratio grows as $N^{1/2}$ whereas the optimized loop architecture grows as $N^{1/4}$, although the gains themselves scale analogically as $N^{1/2}$. The other, more simpler and fixed, architectures are quickly saturating over N , or even worse, the gain-to-instability ratio decreases and remains below one. The effect of losses reduces the SNR, that stops to increase for more than 50% of loss, but at the same time, it increase the stability of the output noise leading to a larger GIR (see Appendix VIII C). This demonstrates this new quantifier's relevance in predicting truly scalable architectures for even slightly different resources. For a comparison, using linear measurements, one could enhance the performances of the architecture by feed-forward strategies [85] or by modifying the type of average at the construc-

tive output port [70] (see Appendix VIII A). However, this potential might be at the cost of even more sophisticated optimization respective to prior knowledge about the input states or a low success rate.

The next step is verifying such scalings experimentally and then extending the theory analysis with experimental tests much more broadly. The current time-multiplexed interference optical experiments [54, 71, 72] with squeezed light are ideal platforms for pioneering proof-of-principle experimental tests with more than a hundred copies needed to predict new scaling of the gain-to-instability ratio.

Subsequently, it is relevant to consider the scalability of Gaussian entangled states and the resources that are needed for large structures of entanglement like cluster states [86–88]. Finally, the scalability of quantum non-Gaussian resources [89] can be predicted theoretically and verified after they become available with sufficient experimental rates for interference experiments. Such diverse investigations can bring the necessary knowledge to operationally navigate experiments towards more scalable and reliable architectures in even slightly unstable conditions. Once these scalable interferences are experimentally tested, the analysis of the figures of merit in applications of squeezed states will ensue, enabling valuable comparisons with the scalability of SNR.

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VIII. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

A. Harmonic mean strategy

A possible solution to enhance the interference effects is to allow for a protocol that is implementing an harmonic mean of the quadrature variance instead of the arithmetic mean of the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop protocols. Such protocol has been proposed and experimentally tested in quantum optics [70]. In this harmonic mean protocol, the N input states interfere on an beam-splitter architecture similar to the pyramidal architecture of Fig.2a, the amplitude quadratures of the

FIG. 5. By changing the protocol allowing for conditional measurement on all output modes but the constructive modes, one can change further enhance the scaling capability. Indeed, not only does the SNR slightly improve but, more importantly, the GIR improve by order of magnitudes. This confirms the predictions that this harmonic averaging of the second order moment enhance the stability of the constructive output squeezed state. In green is the harmonic mean and in blue the deterministic protocol.

FIG. 6. The different quantities involved in the numerical evaluation of SNR and GIR are displayed : (a) is the plot of the mean signal, (b) is the plot of the noise, (c) is the plot of the standard deviation of the SNR. Figures show that the scaling of the SNR comes from the signal and that the accumulation of the noise in the interferometer is not sufficient to compromise the scaling. However, the standard deviation of the SNR is critical in the GIR scaling. Remarkably, only a slightly increase of the standard deviation of the SNR in the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architecture (orange dots) is responsible for the $N^{1/4}$ scaling for the GIR.

$N - 1$ outputs are measured and conditioned to be arbitrarily close to zero. The constructive output state has a displacement equal to $\sqrt{N}x_0$ of the combined initial displacement x_0 of the input states and a variance that is, by construction, equal to $(\Delta x_{out}^2)^{-1} = 1/N \sum_i (\Delta x_i^2)^{-1}$. Hence, for amplitude quadrature squeezed input states with individual squeezing $r_i = r_0 + \delta r_i$, the output SNR writes

$$\text{SNR}_{out,harm}^{(N)} = x_0 e_0^r \sqrt{\sum_i^N e^{+2\delta r_i}}. \quad (10)$$

By numerical evaluation, this protocol provides, a multiplicative enhancement over the averaging SNR for the passive pyramidal protocol and maintain a \sqrt{N} scaling (see Fig.5a). However, it performs far better in the GIR as it maintain the \sqrt{N} scaling but with a multiplicative factor 2 orders of magnitude larger compared to the passive pyramidal architecture presented in the main text (see Fig.5b). Hence, as the costs of this conditional harmonic protocol does not show significantly in the gain, its advantage over the deterministic pyramidal, sequen-

tial and dynamical loop protocols are clear in the more advance statistical evaluation provided by the GIR.

B. Fixed loop strategy analysis

In the fixed loop architecture, the scaling law is hidden in the fraction appearing on the right hand side of Eq.(8). As this term strongly depends on the value of the transmittance t of the beam splitter, one should optimize the numerator of Eq.(8) in order to maximize the value of the mean displacement. The transmittance $t = t^*$ is a function of the number of input modes N and can be found as the roots of a polynomial function in of order N . The numerical simulations for displaying the $\langle \text{SNR} \rangle$ and the $\text{GIR} = \langle \text{SNR} \rangle / \Delta \text{SNR}$ are the orange curves in Fig.3. The behaviour of the mean SNR follows a similar scaling law proportional to $N^{1/2}$ as for the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures above. However, the GIR is closer to a scaling law of order $N^{1/4}$. As visible on Fig.6(b), it is the standard deviation ΔSNR that is critical in the limitation of the scaling for the

loop architecture. Indeed, even a slight increase in the ΔSNR can seriously limit the scaling laws in the GIR, even if ΔSNR (in orange) is only twice larger than for the pyramidal, sequential and dynamical loop architectures above (in blue). This supports the relevance of the GIR to assess critical scaling behaviours.

C. Effect of losses on the scalability

As our main paper aim to emphasize the role played by the noise instability in the scaling laws, we considered the case of a large number of input pure states interfere on interferometers. However, losses are a critical and unavoidable feature in all optics experiments and are expected to limit, possibly even more than the noise instability, the performance of the protocols. Hence, we consider here the effect of such losses by introducing a pure loss channel, where the input state is interacting with the vacuum through a beam splitter of transmittance η , at the input of *each* beam splitter in the pyramidal architecture. We evaluate the output signal, noise, SNR and GIR of our protocols for different values of η . As expected, the losses severely reduce the scalability in the SNR (see Fig.7). However, it is important for an experimental verification that for $\eta > 0.5$, the scaling law is conserved and that only the prefactor is reduced. This behaviour is expected as the loss channel reduces both the signal and the noise. Simultaneously, as the rise of the SNR is worse, the GIR is smaller for larger values of η (see Fig.7). Indeed, the losses are stabilizing the protocol closer to classical limit and as mentioned in the paper, the GIR becomes very large for classical stable states.

D. Fit parameter values

Architecture	x_0	r_0	σ_r	a	b
Pyramidal	2	2	0.125	15	0.50
Loop	2	2	0.125	15	0.49
Loop (N-1)/N	2	2	0.125	14	0.48
Pyramidal	0.5	2	0.5	2.9	0.50
Loop	0.5	2	0.5	3.0	0.48
Loop (N-1)/N	0.5	2	0.5	2.9	0.47
Pyramidal	0.5	2	0.25	3.5	0.50
Loop	0.5	2	0.25	3.5	0.49
Loop (N-1)/N	0.5	2	0.25	3.3	0.48
Pyramidal	0.5	1	0.5	1.1	0.50
Loop	0.5	1	0.5	1.1	0.49
Loop (N-1)/N	0.5	1	0.5	1.0	0.48
Pyramidal	0.1	1	0.5	0.217	0.496
Loop	0.1	1	0.5	0.220	0.481
Loop (N-1)/N	0.1	1	0.5	0.213	0.474

TABLE I. Exponential Fit function aN^b and fitting parameters for $\langle\text{SNR}\rangle$.

Architecture	x_0	r_0	σ_r	a	b
Pyramidal	2	2	0.125	9.8	0.46
Loop	2	2	0.125	18	0.25
Loop (N-1)/N	2	2	0.125	19	0.038
Pyramidal	0.5	2	0.5	1.5	0.51
Loop	0.5	2	0.5	3.5	0.27
Loop (N-1)/N	0.5	2	0.5	3.7	0.10
Pyramidal	0.5	2	0.25	2.7	0.57
Loop	0.5	2	0.25	8.8	0.23
Loop (N-1)/N	0.5	2	0.25	8.4	0.043
Pyramidal	0.5	1	0.5	1.3	0.53
Loop	0.5	1	0.5	4.0	0.21
Loop (N-1)/N	0.5	1	0.5	4.3	0.050
Pyramidal	0.1	1	0.5	1.9	0.47
Loop	0.1	1	0.5	3.5	0.27
Loop (N-1)/N	0.1	1	0.5	4.9	0.054

TABLE II. Exponential Fit function aN^b and fitting parameters for $\text{GIR} = \langle\text{SNR}\rangle/\Delta\text{SNR}$.

FIG. 7. SNR and GIR for the pyramidal architecture with pure loss channel added in the input of each beam splitter. The round dots are numerical simulations for the squeezed states and the triangles are the numerical simulation of the classical states. The addition of pure loss on the input of each beam-splitter in the dynamical, sequential and dynamical loop architecture, significantly reduces the SNR. For a transmittivity of about $\eta = 0.8$, the SNR is reduced to the classically attainable SNR. Hence, losses makes the SNR to loose their squeezing advantage even for relatively small losses. On the other hand, it stabilizes the noise and hence makes the GIR to be significantly higher than the loss-less case.

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